

Original Article

Predictors of Discharge against Medical Advice in a Neonatal Intensive Care Unit in Southern Nigeria

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ABSTRACT

Discharge against medical advice (DAMA) has medical, ethical and legal implications. While the medical team should always act in the best interest of a child, parents realize they have autonomy to decide when a child should be discharged especially when they are responsible for paying the medical bills. The reasons for DAMA in a neonatal unit can vary from one patient to another and the decision can be influenced by a number of factors. The aim of the study was to determine the prevalence of DAMA and the factors that predict the likelihood of DAMA in the neonatal unit of the Delta State University Teaching Hospital, Oghara. A review of all the cases of DAMA in the neonatal unit of the Delta State University Teaching Hospital from 1st January 2018 to 31st December 2019 was undertaken. Data extracted from medical records included gender, admitting weight, gestational age, mode of delivery, place of delivery, parity and diagnosis. Other data included maternal educational level and father's occupation. The collected data were entered into Microsoft Excel spreadsheet and data analysis was by IBM SPSS Statistics for Windows, version 23. One hundred and eighty neonates were admitted over the period under review with 104 (57.8%) males and 76 (42.2%) females. Forty-five (25%) neonates were preterm neonates with respiratory distress syndrome (RDS), 37 (20.6%) had neonatal sepsis, 36 (20%) had birth asphyxia and 32 (17.8%) had congenital anomalies. There were 42 (23.3%) DAMA cases with more DAMA cases recorded among female neonates ($p=0.12$), vaginally delivered neonates ($p=0.018$) and neonates with birth asphyxia ($p=0.012$). The prevalence of DAMA at the study centre was high with vaginal delivery and asphyxia been the most important predictors of DAMA. The treatment outcome of neonates DAMA is unknown. Counseling of parents against DAMA at the time of admission and afterwards should be initiated for parents of neonates with a high likelihood of been DAMA

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INTRODUCTION

The ultimate goal of managing a patient on admission is to ensure return of health to pre-morbid or near pre-morbid state, a state considered fit for discharge by the medical team. However, there are situations where parents

exercise their powers of autonomy and request for their children to be discharged against medical advice (DAMA). Parental autonomy is the right of a parent to raise his or her child and to make all decisions concerning that child free from governmental intervention, unless the child's health and welfare are going to be in jeopardy.¹ Discharge against medical advice has medical, ethical and legal implications especially for a neonates whose clinical presentation can often be protean, and sometimes difficult to predict.² In many situations of DAMA, parents and the medical team do not agree on what is best for the child or what can jeopardize the health of the child. In other instances of DAMA, parents decide to try other options because of their inability to continue to pay for medical bills or because of their cultural perception or believes about child's condition.^{3,4}

The Nigerian constitution through the Child's Right Act states clearly that every child has a right to health, and in a situation where parental decision seems to compromise the health and welfare of a child, then the court should provide legal backing for the managing team to act in the best interest of the child.⁵ However, the constitution has no provisions to pay the child's medical bills should in case the parents decided to abandon the child. Also, due to the fact that neonatal intensive care is capital intensive and most parents have to pay out-of-pocket to foot the medical bills, it becomes even more challenging to convince parents to continue care when they no longer intend to do so.

The problems associated with DAMA are numerous and are often difficult to assess. After parental DAMA, the health condition of the child may deteriorate at home, the child is usually lost to follow up, other health benefits such as immunization may be ignored by the parents and the child may die from medical complications or represent to the hospital or another health facility with a more severe medical condition.^{6,7} A few studies have been done on DAMA in neonatal units and they mainly focused on the

prevalence of DAMA and the reasons for DAMA.^{3,4,8,9}

None of these previous studies on DAMA in a neonatal unit determined the factors that predict the likelihood of DAMA in a neonatal unit. A knowledge of these factors that predict the likelihood of DAMA in a neonatal unit will help the managing team to initiate counseling against DAMA early enough so as to prevent this unfortunate incident. The aim of the study was to determine the prevalence of DAMA and the factors that predict the likelihood of DAMA in the neonatal unit of the Delta State University Teaching Hospital.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

The study was conducted in Delta State University Teaching Hospital (DELSUTH). Delta state is one of the 36 states of the Federal Republic of Nigeria, and is located in the south-south geopolitical zone of the country. The DELSUTH is a tertiary hospital that serves as a referral centre for primary and secondary health facilities in Delta state. As at the time of the study, the NICU had a capacity to admit about 18 neonates with an inborn and an out-born section. The NICU was equipped with mechanical ventilators, radiant heaters, piped oxygen, and other equipments and devices for cardiopulmonary support of unstable neonates. The unit was headed by two neonatologists with support from resident doctors on neonatology postings and paediatric nurses.

The study was a review of the admission records of neonates admitted into the NICU from 1st January 2018 to 31st December 2019. All cases admitted into the unit during the period under review were identified by hospital numbers on the admission register. Relevant data were collected from the case files and they included; gender, age, admitting weight, place of birth, mode of birth, mother's educational level, father's occupation, diagnosis, parity, maternal age and treatment outcome (DAMA, deaths, discharged or referred). Data was entered into

Microsoft Excel spreadsheet and data analysis was by IBM SPSS Statistics for Windows, version 23. Frequencies and percentages of categorical variables were obtained while means and standard deviations were determined for continuous variables. The prevalence of DAMA, the factors associated with DAMA and the likelihood of DAMA were determined. The level of significance for statistical analysis was set at a p -value < 0.05 .

RESULTS

One hundred and eighty neonates were admitted over the period under review with 104 (56.7%) males, 76 (42.3%) preterm neonates and 71 (39.4%) neonates delivered via caesarean section as shown in table I. Most neonates were delivered in health facilities as shown in figure 1

Table I: Distribution into gender, maturity, place of delivery, mode of delivery and parity

Variable	Frequency (%)
Gender	
Male	104 (56.7)
Female	76 (42.2)
Maturity	
Preterm	070 (38.9)
Term	110 (61.1)
Place of delivery	
Health facility	168 (93.3)
Home	012 (6.7)
Mode of delivery	
Vaginal delivery	109 (60.6)
Caesarean Section	71 (39.4)
Parity:	
Primipara	058 (32.3)
Multipara	098 (54.4)
Grandmultipara	024 (13.3)

Figure 1: Distribution of places of delivery of neonates

Eighty-nine (49.4%) neonates were admitted within the first 24 hours of life, 67 (37.2) were admitted between day the 2nd-7th day of life and 24 (13.3) were admitted between 8th -28th day of life. Also, the age range of neonates was 1-672 hours, the mean weight was 2.42 (0.95) kg, the mean gestational age was 37.19 (3.95) weeks and the mean maternal age was 30.51 (5.96) years.

One hundred and two (57%) of mothers had only primary level of education, 60 (33%) had secondary level of education and only 18 (10%) had tertiary level of education.

Twenty-four (14%) fathers were either unemployed or unskilled labourers, one hundred and sixteen (65%) fathers were skilled workers/self-employed, and 38 (21%) fathers were professionals.

There were 71 (39.4%) discharges, 54 (30%) deaths, 42 (23.3%) were DAMA and 13 (7.3%) referred cases.

In all forty-two cases of DAMA, parents documented financial constraint as the main reason for signing against medical advice.

More DAMA cases were recorded among female neonates than male neonates but the differences was not statistically significant. DAMA cases were significantly more associated with neonates with birth asphyxia and neonates delivered vaginally as shown in table II.

On further analysis using logistic regression, vaginally delivered neonates were 2.9 times more likely to be DAMA (AOR = 2.9; %95 CI = 1.3-6.8; $p = 0.012$) and neonates delivered asphyxiated were 6.7 times more likely to be DAMA (AOR = 6.7; %95 CI = 1.3-34.4; $p = 0.023$) as shown in table III.

Available data revealed that neonates DAMA do not return to the facility for follow up, neither are there any medical records to show that these neonates were readmitted. Therefore the treatment outcome of these neonates is unknown to the managing team.

Table II: Associations between DAMA and some variables

Variable	DOMA (%)	DAMA (%)	df	X ²	p- value
Gender					
Male	84 (80.8)	20 (19.2)	1	2.31	0.128
Female	54 (71.1)	22 (28.9)			
Maturity					
Preterm	51 (73.9)	18 (26.1)	1	0.47	0.491
Term	87 (78.4)	24 (21.6)			
Mode of delivery					
Vaginal delivery	77 (70.6)	32 (29.4)	1	5.61	0.018
Caesarean section	61 (78.4)	10 (14.1)			
Place of delivery					
Inborn	46 (80.7)	11 (19.3)	3	3.05	0.384
Secondary health facility	43 (81.1)	10 (18.9)			
Primary health facility	40 (69.0)	18 (31.0)			
Home	9 (75.0)	3 (25.0)			
Morbidities					
Respiratory distress syndrome	33 (73.3)	12 (26.7)	5	14.61	0.012
Neonatal sepsis	32 (86.5)	5 (13.5)			
Asphyxia	20 (55.6)	16 (44.4)			
Congenital anomalies	26 (81.3)	6 (18.8)			
Neonatal jaundice	10 (90.9)	1 (9.1)			
Others	17 (89.5)	2 (10.5)			
Level of Education					
Tertiary	6 (66.7)	3 (33.3)	2	5.10	0.277
Secondary	21 (70.0)	9 (30.0)			
Primary	41 (78.4)	11 (21.6)			

DOMA- Discharge on medical advice; DAMA- Discharge against medical advice

Table III: Logistic Regression on Discharge against Medical Advise

Variable	B	S.E	Wald	Df	Sig	Exp (B)	95% C.I for EXP (B)	
							Lower	Upper
Gender (Male)	-.416	.381	1.194	1	.275	.660	.313	1.391
Vaginal delivery	1.080	.428	6.378	1	.012	2.944	1.273	6.805
Morbidity class			14.081	5	.015			
RDS	1.161	.832	1.944	1	.163	3.192	.625	16.316
NNS	.090	.903	.010	1	.920	1.095	.186	6.429
Asphyxia	1.903	.835	5.199	1	.023	6.705	1.306	34.416
Congenital anomalies	.522	.888	.346	1	.556	1.686	.296	9.607
NNJ	-.232	1.303	.032	1	.858	.793	.062	10.188
Constant	-2.573	.845	9.272	1	.002	.076		

RDS- Respiratory distress syndrome; NNS- Neonatal sepsis; NNJ- Neonatal jaundice

DISCUSSION

The prevalence of DAMA from the present study was 23.3%. The prevalence is higher than most reported prevalence in the literature both locally and globally.^{3-4,8,9} However, the prevalence obtained in the present study is comparable to 25.4% reported in Gujarat, India.¹⁰ The reason for the high prevalence of DAMA

at the study centre was not certain but most parents documented financial constraints as their reason for DAMA. Other reasons for DAMA included; perceived healthy status of neonate, need to seek alternative treatment, no response to treatment. Other studies carried out in Nigeria also reported financial

constraint as the commonest reason for DAMA.^{3,4,11,12} Cost of neonatal medical care in Nigeria can be quite high especially in the tertiary institutions with neonatal intensive care units. The overall cost of neonatal care for a neonate on admission can range from \$211.1 to \$1573.9 in a public tertiary health facility.¹³ There is presently no study on cost of neonatal care at the study centre, however, some of the commonly used items parents pay for in the NICU include; oxygen therapy-N6000, SPO₂ probe-N10,000, mechanical ventilator- N2000 per day, daily care-N1000 beside medications and investigations. In a country where more than 40% of the population lives below the poverty line, then certainly very few can afford to pay out-of-pocket for neonatal care in Nigeria.¹⁴ However, most studies outside Nigeria sited other reason beside finance as the major reasons for DAMA. This is because the government or insurance systems were responsible for paying for health in these centres.^{2,15,16} The study carried out in Gujarat India, with a high prevalence of DAMA, reported financial constraint as the most common reason for DAMA due to the fact that affected parents paid medical bills out-of-pocket. There were more female neonates DAMA than male neonates despite the fact that there were more male neonates admitted during the period under review. The difference between DAMA for female neonates and DAMA for male neonates was not statistically significant. However, it thus appear that parents showed some bias against female neonates and were more likely to discharge them against medical advice than male neonates. A similar finding was reported by Onankpa and colleagues in Sokoto, northwestern Nigeria.³ This trend needs to be further evaluated as it portrays a grave implication for a country already with so much gender inequality. Neonates delivered vaginally were significantly more likely to be DAMA than neonates delivered by caesarean section. Other studies have reported a similar finding.^{3,15,16} The reason for this finding may

be due to the fact that mothers who delivered vaginally recovered earlier and were discharged earlier than mothers who had caesarean section. It thus appear to be a matter of convenience that these neonates delivered vaginally were DAMA as the mothers felt since they no longer needed medical care, their neonates should be discharged home with them.

Neonates with birth asphyxia were significantly more DAMA when compared to other neonates. A similar finding was reported in the literature by other authors.^{3,4} Birth asphyxia may present with very subtle findings that may not be obvious to these parents and they may not see the reason why their neonates should continue medical care when they appear apparently healthy. Also, severely asphyxiated neonates are more likely to stay longer on admission than many other neonatal conditions as a result, parents are likely to experience financial fatigue or burn out and discharge their neonates against medical advice.

Asphyxiated neonates were about 6.7 times more likely to be DAMA when compared to other neonates, while neonates delivered vaginally were 2.7 times more likely to be DAMA when compared to their caesarean section counterparts.

CONCLUSION

The prevalence of DAMA at the study centre was high with vaginal delivery and asphyxia been the most important predictors of DAMA. The treatment outcome of neonates DAMA is unknown. Counseling of parents against DAMA at the time of admission and afterwards should be initiated for neonates with a high likelihood of been DAMA

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